

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style and Religiosity on Employee Performance Through Work Motivation of PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Employees Jember

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Abstract

The need for quality human resources is very important for PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember to achieve its main goals. The development of an institution is determined by the performance of its teachers and employees, which ultimately affects the productivity and improvement of the quality of the institution's human resources. Good performance can be achieved through a transformational leadership style and good religiosity through the work motivation of teachers and employees. Many studies have been conducted to examine the relationship between transformational leadership style and religiosity on employee performance. However, some of them have not shown success and there are research gaps. The research results have a big influence on the performance assessment of PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember employees. This research tries to measure the performance of teachers and employees from transformational leadership style and religiosity and work motivation as intervention variables. This decision making is based on existing theory. In fact, the role of transformational leadership style and religiosity by assessing employee performance through work motivation is expected to be able to make teachers and employees of PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember better compared to Islamic boarding schools in other areas that have achieved their goals.

Keywords: transformational leadership style, religiosity, employee performance, work motivation.

INTRODUCTION

The Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember Islamic Boarding School is a religious educational institution founded by Kyai Haji Ali Rahbini on June 2 1991 and is still under his leadership. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic boarding school is an Islamic-based educational institution that combines traditional education systems with modern systems located in Jember Regency with the address Jl Beringin No 12 Sumber Bulus 1 Ledokombo. The Nurul Ali Islamic boarding school education system includes formal and non-formal institutions. Formal education consists of Mts Nurul Ali and MA Nurul Ali while non-formal education is MMU Nurul Ali branch of Sidogiri B-18, Ma'had Tahfidzul Qur'an and regular recitation of the book Al-Miftah Lil'Ulum.

The existing phenomenon is that the Nurul Ali Islamic boarding school has a classification of Madrasah Diniyah and Tahfidz teachers as well as Madrasah Aliyah and Madrasah Tsanawiyah teachers, all of whom are non-PNS. The situations and conditions found in MA and Mts teachers cause their focus to be divided and ultimately affect work achievement. Decreased motivation is also a trigger that causes a decline in the performance of teachers and employees, thus in running educational institutions, especially Islamic boarding schools, it is felt necessary to provide reciprocity for the contributions made by teachers and employees in carrying out their duties in order to realize the expected goals. Therefore, the attention of Islamic boarding school institutions in providing support and training to employee teachers is very necessary. If teachers and employees experience a decrease in motivation, employee performance will tend to decline.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership Style

Burns (1977) states that transformational leadership is leadership that focuses on change towards continuous improvement. Transformational leadership tends to be normative, centralized, authoritarian, consistent and charismatic (authority). Transformational leadership encourages leaders to develop tools and strategies to encourage all stakeholders, to participate in the mission and commit to the school's goals.

Bass and Avolio (1994) proposed four components in a person's level of leadership with the 4i concept which means the following:

1. Idealized influence, which is explained as behavior that generates respect and trust from the people they lead. Idealized influence means sharing risks, through consideration of needs that are placed above personal needs, and moral and ethical behavior.
2. Inspirational motivation, which is reflected in behavior that always provides challenge and meaning to the work of the people led, including behavior that is able to articulate clear expectations, and behavior that is able to demonstrate commitment to organizational goals. This spirit is generated through enthusiasm and optimism.
3. Intellectual stimulation. Leaders who demonstrate this type of leadership always explore new ideas and creative solutions from the people they lead. He also always encourages new approaches to doing work. Intellectual stimulation is the process of a

leader to increase his followers' awareness of various problems, and influence his followers to solve these problems with new perspectives.

4. Individualized consideration, which is reflected by leaders who always listen attentively and pay special attention to the achievement needs and needs of the people they lead. Individual attention is support, encouragement, and providing experiences for followers to achieve more.

Religiosity

Mangunwijaya (1982) states that religiosity is an aspect that an individual has internalized in his heart, the vibration of his personal conscience and personal attitudes. Religiosity is a real manifestation or quality of a person's religiousness. In this opinion, religiosity looks more at aspects of conscience (qalb), personal attitudes, and tastes that encompass the totality (including reason and human feelings) of the human person.

Glock and Stark (1968) stated that the dimensions of religiosity are as follows:

1. The dimension of belief (the ideological dimension). the ideological dimension is based on the expectation that a religion will adhere to certain beliefs" (i.e., recognized doctrines).
2. The ritualistic dimension of worship practices. The ritual realm involves the experience of worship
3. The experiential dimension. The experiential dimension focuses on personal experiences of faith, perhaps transcendent encounters.
4. The intellectual dimension, the intellectual dimension is related to the hope that religious people will be given information and knowledge about the basic principles of their teachings, faith, and sacred scriptures such as history, sacraments, and morality.
5. The consequential dimension, a dimension that refers to the influence of the religious values one adheres to which have a positive influence on one's daily life.

Work Motivation

Mangkunegara (2013) states that motive or motivation is an internal driving force to carry out activities to achieve goals. Changes in energy within a person's self (person) which are characterized by the emergence of feelings and reactions to achieve goals. Mangkunegara (2013) also states that motivation is a change in energy within a person which is characterized by the emergence of "feelings" and is preceded by a response to a goal.

According to Maslow, quoted by Hasibuan (2008), explains that employee work motivation is influenced by indicators to determine employee work motivation, namely:

1. Physiological or physical needs, shown by giving bonuses, food money, transportation money, and so on.
2. Security, demonstrated by work security and safety facilities, including social security for workers, pension funds, health benefits, health insurance and work safety equipment.
3. Social, demonstrated by interacting with other people, including establishing harmonious working relationships, the need to be accepted in a group and the need to love and be loved.
4. Respect, shown by recognition and appreciation based on ability, namely the need to be respected and appreciated by other employees and leaders for their work performance.
5. Self-actualization, shown by the interesting and challenging nature of the work, where the employee will mobilize his skills, abilities, abilities and potential. Companies can fulfill this need by providing education and training.

Employee performance

Pabundu (2006) states that performance is a work result produced by an employee which is interpreted to achieve the expected goals. Performance can also be interpreted as the result of the work function/activities of a person or group in an organization which is influenced by various factors to achieve organizational goals within a certain time period. This understanding will not emphasize individual performance but also group performance.

According to Bernardin and Russell (2011: 382), there are six criteria for assessing employee performance:

1. Quality, namely the level at which the process or adjustment to the ideal way of carrying out activities or fulfilling activities meets expectations.
2. Quantity, namely the amount produced which is realized through currency value, number of units, or number of activity cycles that have been completed.
3. Timeliness, namely the level at which activities have been completed in a faster time than specified and maximizing the time available for other activities.
4. Cost effectiveness, namely the level at which the use of company resources in the form of humans, finances and technology is maximized to obtain the highest results or reduce losses from each unit.
5. Need for supervision, namely the degree to which a worker can carry out a job function without requiring the supervision of a supervisor to prevent undesirable actions.
6. Interpersonal impact, namely the degree to which employees maintain self-esteem, good name and cooperation among colleagues and subordinates without distinguishing between social status.

LITERATURE REVIEW

LITERATURE REVIEW

RESEARCH CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK**The influence of transformational leadership style on PP employee performance. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember**

According to Wahidya (2020), transformational leaders have a significant influence on improving organizational performance. A transformational leader is a person who stimulates and inspires (changes) followers to achieve extraordinary results. The research results of Ade Rio et al (2020) in their research state that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. These results show that the greater the transformational leadership style at work, the more employee performance will increase.

H1: Transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher and employee performance.

The influence of religiosity on the performance of PP employees. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember

According to (Iqbal 2021) the level of religiosity is positively correlated with a person's level of performance. Several experts also argue that worship can produce this energy, one of which is James, who stated that this spiritual energy can influence a person's psychology and physiology. The results of Hendi et al (2020) in their research are that religiosity has a significant effect on employee performance. These results show that the greater the religiosity at work, the greater the employee's performance will increase.

H2: Religiosity has a positive and significant effect on teacher and employee performance.

The influence of transformational leadership style on PP work motivation. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember

According to John and Gregory (2012), leadership plays an important role in motivating employees, and employee work motivation has an impact on employee performance. Anne et al. (2008) stated that leadership greatly influences employee performance with work motivation as an intervening variable. The results of Augustine's (2022) research are that transformational leadership has a significant effect on work motivation. These results show that the greater the transformational leadership style at work, the greater the work motivation.

H3: Transformational leadership style has a positive and significant effect on teacher and employee performance

The influence of religiosity on PP's work motivation. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember

According to Wibowo (2007:379) concludes that motivation is an encouragement to a series of human behavioral processes in achieving goals, in which there are elements that generate, direct, maintain, demonstrate, intensity, are continuous and purposeful. Religion or religiosity requires adherents to deepen their teachings, strengthen their beliefs and carry out orders according to applicable rules and stay away from the prohibitions contained in their teachings. The results of Dini et al (2021) in their research

state that religiosity has a positive and significant effect on work motivation. These results show that the greater the religiosity at work, the greater the work motivation.

H4: Religiosity has a positive and significant effect on teacher and employee performance.

The influence of transformational leadership style on PP employee performance. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember through work motivation

The research results of Agustine et al (2021), in their research, work motivation was able to encourage the strength of the transformational leadership style variable on employee performance by 0.00. Shows the magnitude of the influence of transformational leadership style on work motivation of 0.00% so that there is an indirect influence between transformational leadership style variables on employee performance through work motivation which is included in the strong category or in other words work motivation is able to mediate transformational leadership style on employee performance .

H5: Work motivation strengthens the relationship between transformational leadership style and teacher and employee performance

The influence of religiosity on the performance of PP employees. Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember through work motivation.

The research results of Dini et al (2021), in their research, work motivation was able to encourage the strength of the religiosity variable on employee performance by 0.00. Shows the magnitude of the influence of religiosity on work motivation of 0.00% so that there is an indirect influence between the religiosity variable on employee performance through work motivation which is included in the strong category or in other words work motivation is able to mediate religiosity on employee performance.

H6: Work motivation strengthens the relationship between religiosity and teacher and employee performance

The influence of work motivation on employee performance at PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember

According to Sunyoto (2012), providing motivation to employees or individuals of course has objectives including: encouraging employee enthusiasm and passion, increasing employee morale and job satisfaction, increasing employee work productivity, maintaining employee loyalty and stability, increasing discipline and reducing employee absenteeism levels, creating a good working atmosphere and relationships, increasing employee creativity and participation, improving employee welfare, increasing employees' sense of responsibility for their duties and work. The research results of Dewi et al (2020) in their research are that work motivation influences employee performance. These results show that the greater the work motivation at work, the more employee performance will increase.

H7: work motivation has a positive and significant effect on teacher and employee performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research plan

This research is designed to provide an explanation of the cause and effect relationship between variables through hypothesis testing, thus the research approach is a descriptive method in the form of an explanation using a quantitative approach. This type of research is exploratory research, which is a type of research that seeks to find new ideas or relationships. Meanwhile, descriptive research is research that aims to describe the nature or characteristics of a particular phenomenon. Populasi dan sampel

Population

in this research were all 77 teachers and employees of PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember. The sampling method is using a saturated sample method or non-probability sample where all teachers and employees at PP Nurul Ali Ledokombo Jember are sampled.

Data source

The data sources in this research use primary data and secondary data. According to Silalahi (2012: 289), data sources are divided into two sources, namely Primary Data, data taken directly from respondents, including teacher and employee identity data and questionnaires. Secondary data is data obtained from other sources that are related to this research. Secondary data sources can be articles, the internet, journals and so on.

Data analysis method

Outer Model Analysis

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is an indicator that is assessed based on the correlation between the item score/component score and the construct score, which can be seen from the standardized loading factor which describes the magnitude of the correlation between each measurement item (indicator) and the construct. An individual reflexive measure is said to be high if it correlates > 0.7 with the construct to be measured, while an outer loading value between 0.5 - 0.6 is considered sufficient.

2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity is a measurement model with reflexive indicators assessed based on cross loading of measurements with constructs. If the correlation of a construct with a measurement item is greater than the size of another construct, it shows that their block size is better than that of other blocks. Meanwhile, another method for assessing discriminant validity is by comparing the squareroot of average variance extracted (AVE) value.

Composite reliability is an indicator for measuring a construct that can be seen in the latent variable coefficients view. To evaluate composite reliability, there are two measuring tools, namely internal consistency and Cronbach's alpha. In this measurement, if the value achieved is > 0.70 , it can be said that the construct has high reliability.

3. Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's alpha is a reliability test carried out to strengthen the results of composite reliability. A variable can be declared reliable if it has a Cronbach's alpha value > 0.7 .

4. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test was carried out to determine the relationship between indicators. To find out whether the formative indicators experience multicollinearity by knowing the value of the variance inflation factors (VIF). A variance inflation factors (VIF) value between 5-10 can be said to mean that this indicator has multicollinearity

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity has meaning, namely a set of indicators representing a latent variable and underlying that latent variable. To test convergent validity, the outer loading or loading factor value is used. An indicator is declared to meet convergent validity in the good category if the outer loading value is > 0.7 . According to Chin, as quoted by (Ghozali, 2021), an outer loading value between 0.5 - 0.6 is considered sufficient to meet the convergent validity requirements. However, in this study there were results of outer loading that were below 0.3, this can be confirmed by the opinion of Hair et al (2010) which states that measurements are said to achieve convergent validity, in the SEM/PLS approach this is when the factor loading is $> 0,30$.

2. Discriminant Validity

Table 1. Discriminant validity

Variabel	Nilai Cross Loading	R _{tabel}	Information
Transformational Leadership Style (X1)	0.765	0.224	Valid
Religiosity (X2)	0.476	0.224	Valid
Work Motivation (Z)	0.706	0.224	Valid
Employee Performance (Y)	0.290	0.224	Valid

Table 4.1 above shows that there are 62 male respondents (80.5%), the majority of respondents are dominated by male teachers or ustadz who work at MMU-18 institutions, because until now the foundation has not opened recruitment for female teachers or ustazah. Data on 15 female teachers (19.5%) in the research results above comes from the servant alumni program which is required by Islamic boarding schools in accordance with applicable terms and conditions.

3. Composite Reliability

Table 2 Composite Reliability

Variabel	CR	Rule Of thumb	Results
Transformational Leadership Style (X1)	0,847	0,700	Sangat Reliabel
Religiosity (X2)	0,805	0,700	Reliabel
Work Motivation (Z)	0,800	0,700	Reliabel
Employee Performance (Y)	0,749	0,700	Reliabel

Based on the data display in table 4.11 above, it can be seen that the composite reliability value for all research variables is > 0.6 . These results indicate that each variable has met composite reliability so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability

4. Cronbach Alpha

Table 3. Cronbach Alpha

Variabel	CA	Rule Of Thumb	Results
Transformational Leadership Style (X1)	0,754	0,700	Reliabel
Religiosity (X2)	0,706	0,700	Reliabel
Work Motivation (Z)	0,774	0,700	Reliabel
Employee Performance (Y)	0,692	0,700	Cukup Reliabel

Based on the data display above in table 4.12, it can be seen that the Cronbach alpha value of each research variable is > 0.7 except for the employee performance variable whose value is < 0.7 . Thus, these results can show that each variable except the performance of the research employees has met the Cronbach alpha value requirements, so it can be concluded that the three variables have a high level of reliability.

5. Multicollinierity

Table 5. Multicollinierity

Variabel	VIF
Transformational Leadership Style (X1)	2.010
Religiosity (X2)	1.584
Work Motivation (Z)	2.441

Based on the results of the multicollinearity test, it shows that the VIF (Variance Inflation Factors) value is below 10, so it can be said that multicollinearity does not occur for each of the research variables.

HYPOTHESIS TEST

Hypothesis testing in this research was carried out by looking at the T-Statistics values and P-Values values. The research hypothesis can be declared accepted if the P-Values < 0.05. The following are the results of hypothesis testing obtained in this research through the inner model:

The results of testing the direct influence of the relationship between variables using SmartPLS 3.0 can be seen in the following table:

Table 6. Pengaruh Antar Variabel

Variabel	Path Coefficients	P-Value	Results
X1-Y	-0.349	0.035	Significant
X1-Z	0.542	0.000	Significant
X2-Y	0.131	0.272	Not Significant
X2-Z	0.345	0.001	Significant
Z-Y	0.817	0.000	Significant

Based on testing the direct influence of figure 4.1 and table 4.14 above, it can be seen that:

1. The path coefficient value of transformational leadership style (X1) on employee performance (Y) is $\beta = -0.349$, which is negative. The p-value is 0.035, this result is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Based on the calculated values of path coefficients and p-values on the influence between variables, transformational leadership style (X1) is proven to have a negative and significant effect on employee performance (Y).
2. The path coefficient value of transformational leadership style (X1) on work motivation (Z) is $\beta = 0.542$, which is positive. The p-value is 0.000, this result is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. Based on the calculated values of path coefficients and p-values on the influence between variables, transformational leadership style (X1) is proven to have a positive and significant effect on work motivation (Z).
3. The path coefficient value of religiosity (X2) on employee performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.131$, which is positive. The p-value is 0.272, this result is not significant because the p-value is more than 0.05. Based on the calculated values of path coefficients and p-values on the influence between variables, religiosity (X2) is proven to have a positive and insignificant effect on employee performance (Y).
4. The path coefficient value of religiosity (X2) on work motivation (Z) is $\beta = 0.345$, which is positive. The p-value is 0.001, this result is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. So, based on the calculated values of path coefficients and p-values on the influence between variables, religiosity (X2) is proven to have a positive and significant effect on work motivation (Z).
5. The path coefficient value of work motivation (Z) on employee performance (Y) is $\beta = 0.817$, which is positive. The p-value is 0.000, this result is significant because the p-value is less than 0.05. So, based on the calculated values of path coefficients and p-values on the influence between variables, work motivation (Z) is proven to have a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y).

Sobel Test

The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence of the independent variable (X) consisting of transformational leadership style and religiosity on the dependent variable employee performance (Y) through the intervening variable work motivation (Z). The results of the Sobel test calculation are as follows:

$$Sab = \sqrt{b^2S + a^D S b^2 + S a^2 S b^2}$$

a) $\frac{X_1}{Sab} = \frac{ab}{0,10 \quad 0,10} = \frac{0,542 \times 0,817}{0,10 \quad 0,10} = 4,43$

$$b) \quad X_2 = ab = 0,345 \times 0,817 = 0,281 = 2,82$$

Based on the results of the Sobel test calculation, it shows that the z value (X1) is 4.43, the z value (X2) is 2.82 > 1.96 (absolute z value) thus proving that the work motivation variable (Z) is able to mediate relationship between the influence of transformational leadership style (X1) and religiosity (X2) on employee performance (Y).

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that the transformational leadership style has an effect on employee performance by looking at the significance level, namely 0.035. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is negative, meaning that the better the transformational leadership style, the more employee performance will increase (H1 is accepted).

Based on research results, transformational leadership style has a significant effect on the performance of teachers and employees but has a negative effect. This shows that although there is a significant relationship between transformational leadership style and performance, the effect is negative. When Kyai Ali implemented an intense transformational leadership approach, teachers and employees were not ready and unable to adapt to the transformation that occurred, as a result their performance decreased rather than increased. Apart from that, Kyai Ali's traditional leadership style, namely obeying and following Kyai Ali's orders and directions as the leader of the Islamic boarding school, is still common among teachers and employees, so that when Kyai Ali uses a new leadership style they are not ready to innovate and be creative.

Kyai Ali's role in carrying out transformational leadership can only increase the motivation of teachers and employees, because even though he is motivated, the performance of teachers and employees does not increase. The Nurul Ali Islamic Boarding School has a classification of teachers, namely formal and non-formal teachers, formal teachers are teachers who teach at formal educational institutions such as Mts and MA, while non-formal teachers teach students related to religious knowledge at the Nurul Ali Islamic Boarding School. All of the formal teachers are recorded as having non-PNS status and the majority of non-formal teachers are students with the title of ustadz. An effective transformational leader is able to inspire, motivate and direct non-PNS teachers in a way that allows them to achieve high performance, even though they do not have civil servant status, but in the research results the transformational leadership style possessed by Kyai Ali at the Nurul Ali Islamic boarding school is not capable provide a positive influence to improve the performance of teachers and employees.

Even though a leader applies an effective transformational leadership style, the performance of teachers and employees remains stagnant, because teachers and employees lack readiness, lack of resource support, obstacles and challenges that affect performance. In this context, Kyai Ali as the leader of the Islamic boarding school needs to consider a more holistic approach to transformational leadership, ensuring that efforts to motivate teachers and employees are in line with the welfare and practical needs of teachers and employees. This can help avoid negative impacts and result in sustainable performance improvements.

The Effect of Religiosity on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that religiosity has no effect on employee performance by looking at the significance level, namely 0.272. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the religiosity, the employee performance will not increase (H2 is not accepted).

Teachers and employees work in educational institutions under the auspices of Islamic boarding schools. There are two background classifications of teachers and employees, namely formal teachers, some of whom are workers recruited from outside the Islamic boarding school with an educational background in accordance with the job offered, while non-school teachers. Formally some of them are students at the Sidogiri Islamic boarding school who are assigned to teach and are student alumni who are recruited directly by the Islamic boarding school to teach religious knowledge and books at the Islamic boarding school. Different backgrounds can show differences in each individual teacher and employee in understanding the relationship between religiosity and daily work. Even though a teacher and employee have high religiosity and understand religion, their performance as an educator in terms of achievement for students or santri is not consistently better than teachers and employees who have a lower level of religiosity. Teachers and employees understand religious values and teachings according to the culture of the Islamic boarding school and society. They know the importance of implementing religious values, religious knowledge and knowing the good and bad of behavior towards themselves and society, but do not understand how to integrate religious values or religiosity in their duties and work.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Work Motivation

The results of the hypothesis test show that the transformational leadership style has an effect on work motivation by looking at the significance level, namely 0.000. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the transformational leadership style, the more work motivation will increase (H3 is accepted).

Work motivation will be achieved well if the transformational leadership style is implemented well. Kyai Ali is able to provide a sense of trust, inspiration and role model in carrying out daily life so that he is able to provide enthusiasm and motivation in doing his work. Kyai Ali's transformational leadership style which has a positive and significant effect on motivation shows that teachers and employees still need leadership from Kyai Ali in motivating in everyday life. Communication between Kyai Ali and teachers/employees is established in several activities, firstly study activities where this activity is a moment where Kyai Ali provides some knowledge and religious knowledge which of course includes advice and teachings about living life, secondly is a religious celebration event, namely where Kyai Ali gave lectures and advice on a religious celebration theme, and the third was Kyai's nyabis dhalem where the community, teachers and employees visited Kyai Ali directly at home with the intention of establishing friendship and hoping for blessings, so that communication ran well and intensely. These activities, Kyai Ali, can provide ideas, visions and religious inspiration to teachers and employees, so that they can influence their motivation. This is in line

with conditions in the field, which shows that Kyai Ali's transformational leadership has an important role in providing work motivation by providing enthusiasm, encouragement and prayer, so that conditions in a conducive work environment can increase the motivation of teachers and employees.

The Influence of Religiosity on Work Motivation

The results of the hypothesis test show that religiosity has a significant effect on work motivation with a significance of 0.001. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the higher the religiosity, the more work motivation will increase (H4 is accepted).

Work motivation will be achieved well if religiosity is implemented well. The religious values possessed by teachers and employees are able to provide meaning and learning as well as religious insight, so that they can provide enthusiasm and motivation in carrying out daily life, this is because working is an obligation for a Muslim. Therefore, work for someone who has a high level of religiosity is considered not just to carry out a routine, but is also considered as a medium to hope for Allah SWT's blessing so that this motivation will appear automatically within them.

The environmental background of the majority of teachers and employees comes from villages or hamlets close to the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic boarding school, so that the social culture starting from religious traditions, religious paradigms and strong relationships with the Islamic boarding school is very high. This provides a bond of religiosity and religious values between teachers and employees with the Islamic boarding school having the same values and goals. Another background is that the majority of teachers and employees are students, either students who graduated from other Islamic boarding schools or students who graduated from the Nurul Ali Islamic boarding school itself. This will provide a different meaning for teachers and employees where high religiosity will give them high motivation in living their lives. Apart from that, the participation of teachers and employees in Islamic boarding school religious activities such as imtihan, birthday of the Prophet, general studies, and nyabis dhalem can increase religious values in teachers and employees so that they can increase motivation to contribute to society and Islamic boarding schools, especially the educational institutions where they are located. Work.

The Influence of Transformational Leadership Style on Employee Performance Through Work Motivation

The results of the hypothesis test show that work motivation is proven to mediate the influence of the transformational leadership style on employee performance by looking at the Sobel test, namely $4.43 > 1.96$. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the work motivation, the more it will mediate the influence of the transformational leadership style on employee performance will increase (H5 is accepted). The results of this research are in line with research by Ni Made et al (2019), Ahmad (2020), Lusi (2020), Agustine et al (2018), Meltiana et al (2022) concluding that the mediating role of work motivation variables is able to encourage the strength of the variable's influence transformational leadership style on employee performance. So there is an indirect influence between the transformational leadership style variable on employee performance through the work motivation variable which is in the strong category or in other words work motivation is able to moderate the transformational leadership style on employee performance.

The Effect of Religiosity on Employee Performance Through Work Motivation

The results of the hypothesis test show that work motivation is proven to mediate the influence of religiosity on employee performance by looking at the Sobel test, namely $2.82 > 1.96$. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the work motivation, the more mediate the influence of religiosity on employee performance. increases (H6 is accepted). The results of this research are in line with research by Dini et al (2021) concluding that the mediating role of work motivation variables is able to encourage the strength of the influence of religiosity variables on employee performance. So there is an indirect influence between the religiosity variable on employee performance through the work motivation variable which is in the strong category or in other words work motivation is able to moderate religiosity on employee performance.

The Influence of Work Motivation on Employee Performance

The results of the hypothesis test show that work motivation influences employee performance by looking at the significance level, namely 0.000. The influence shown by the regression coefficient is positive, meaning that the better the work motivation, the more employee performance will increase (H7 is accepted).

Employee performance will be achieved well if work motivation is implemented well. Comfort and communication as well as friendship in an established environment increase the work motivation of teachers and employees. Work motivation can come from within the teachers and employees themselves or from external motivation. If a person's motivation at work is high, it can increase their enthusiasm, dedication and quality of teaching, this condition will be very beneficial for the institution, because its performance will increase. Religious-based educational institutions can motivate teachers by providing Islamic boarding school religious activities so that they can understand the important role of teachers and employees in improving the quality of future generations. Thus providing intrinsic motivation which can improve performance. Every year the Nurul Ali Islamic Boarding School always provides training and development to teachers and employees, whether training from the Ministry of Religious Education or from Sidogiri, which is a central Islamic boarding school that has hierarchical and family relationships with the Nurul Ali Islamic Boarding School. This training and development can provide teachers and employees with the opportunity to develop their skills and skills. Teachers and employees will also feel enthusiastic and motivated to improve the quality of teaching, so that it can improve the performance of teachers and employees.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion that the researcher has explained, it can be concluded as follows:

1. The results show that the transformational leadership style has a significant effect on the performance of teachers and employees at the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
2. The results show that religiosity does not significantly influence employee performance for teachers and employees of the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
3. The results show that the transformational leadership style has a significant effect on work motivation at the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
4. The results show that religiosity has a significant effect on work motivation for teachers and employees of the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
5. The results show that the transformational leadership style has a significant effect on employee performance through work motivation for teachers and employees of the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
6. The results show that religiosity has a significant effect on employee performance through work motivation for teachers and employees of the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.
7. The results show that work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance at the Nurul Ali Ledokombo Islamic Boarding School.

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